

DETECTION OF *PHYTOPHTHORA* ON ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES BY A NEW NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING (NGS) APPROACH

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We have tested different primer sets to be used by NGS approach using Illumina platform to assess *Phytophthora* populations in environmental samples. PCR amplifications of ITS1 and ITS2 (two primer sets), *cox1* gene (1 primer set), *cox2* gene (2 primer sets) and *cox1-2* spacer (1 primer set) have been tested with DNA extracted from soil and bark of infected trees using direct or nested PCR approaches. Results indicated good amplification for direct PCR with four ITS primer sets and one *cox2* set as well as using a second-round PCR approach with one ITS and one *cox2* primer sets. The genes were amplified and barcode-multiplexed from the different DNA samples and then subjected to Illumina MiSeq sequencing. Amplification with *cox2* or *cox1-2* spacer failed, but good amplification was obtained for *cox1* region either using direct or second-round PCR approach. Initial bioinformatics analyses indicated that although direct PCR targeting ITS regions is more convenient for methodological purposes it can oversight the presence of *Phytophthora* spp. on the samples. On the contrary direct amplification of the *cox1* region using primers *cox1levup/cox1levlo* and partial bidirectional amplification of the amplicons or nested-PCR amplification of *cox1* using *cox1levup/cox1levlo* in the 1st round and *HVshort/cox1levlo* in the 2nd round and complete bidirectional sequencing allowed detection of several *Phytophthora* spp. and other oomycetes in soil and wood samples. Comparison of results obtained with this new protocol targeting the *cox1* region with that from Scibetta et al. (2012) using a nested approach targeting the ITS region is under progress.